

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF FRICTIONAL FORCES
BETWEEN DIFFERENT COMBINATIONS OF ARCHWIRE
BRACKETS**Dr. Sobia Rehman¹, Dr. Tayybah Tahira², Dr. Anum Rashid³, Dr. Mohsin Majeed⁴^{1,2,4}Nishtar Institute of Dentistry, Multan³Lahore Medical & Dental College, Lahore

Article Received: October 2020

Accepted: November 2020

Published: December 2020

Abstract:

Introduction: During sliding mechanics, frictional resistance is an important counterforce for orthodontic tooth movement; which must be controlled to allow the application of light continuous forces.

Objective: To test the static and kinetic frictional resistance between three orthodontic brackets: ceramic, self-ligating and stainless steel, and three arches 0.019×0.025 ": stainless steel, nickel-titanium, titanium-molybdenum.

Place and Duration: This study was conducted at the Orthodontics department of Nishtar dental Hospital, Multan for one-year duration from June 2019 to June 2020.

Materials and Methods: An in vitro study compared the effect of stainless steel, nickel titanium, and beta titanium arcs on the frictional forces of three orthodontic bracket systems: ceramic, self-ligating and stainless-steel brackets. All brackets had 0.022 "slots and the wires were 0.019×0.025 ". Friction was assessed in a simulated semi-arc fixed apparatus on a testing machine. The static and kinetic friction data were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Duncan's multi-range post-hoc test.

Result: Self-ligating (Damon) brackets generated significantly lower static and kinetic frictional forces than stainless steel (Gemini) and ceramic (Clarity) brackets. Among the arc materials, beta-titanium showed the maximum friction force, and stainless-steel arches had the lowest friction force.

Conclusion: The static and kinetic frictional force of the stainless-steel bracket was lowest in each wire combination.

Keywords: beta-titanium wire, frictional resistance, kinetic friction, self-ligating, static friction

Corresponding author:**Dr. Sobia Rehman,**

Nishtar Institute of Dentistry, Multan

QR code

Please cite this article in press Sobia Rehman et al, *Comparative Assessment Of Frictional Forces Between Different Combinations Of Archwire Brackets.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(12).

INTRODUCTION:

The increasing use of sliding mechanics in orthodontics has led to considerable research interest in friction¹. Friction is an important factor in sliding mechanics; friction occurs during the retraction of the teeth into the extraction area, active torque, leveling and alignment as the arc has to move through the gaps of the bracket¹⁻³. During sliding mechanics, biological tissue reacts and tooth movement only occurs when applied forces exceed the friction at the joint of the bracket wire⁴⁻⁵. Initially, the static friction between the arc wire and the bracket must be overcome to initiate tooth movement, then as the tooth moves, dynamic friction occurs as the arc wire is guided in the direction of the applied force as it is guided through the gaps of the bracket⁶⁻⁷. Therefore, this study was conducted to evaluate the static and kinetic frictional forces of different types of brackets (stainless steel, ceramic and self-ligating steel) with different arc wire systems (stainless steel, NiTi and Beta Titanium or TMA) and to compare the static and kinetic friction forces between different combinations of arcs and locks.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This study was conducted at the Orthodontics department of Nishtar dental Hospital, Multan for one-year duration from June 2019 to June 2020. The study was conducted to evaluate the friction between different types of orthodontic brackets and orthodontic wires. All brackets used in the study were pre-adjusted 0.022" gaps in the following varieties: stainless steel (Gemini, 3M Unitek), ceramic (Clarity, 3M Unitek) and self-ligating (Damon SLII, Ormco). Wires with dimensions of 0.019 × 0.025" were used in the following types: stainless steel (SS), nickel-titanium (Ni-Ti) and titanium-molybdenum alloy (TMA). Rectangular ducts were selected for this study as they provide control in all three planes of space. A universal testing machine (Instron, Model-5848) was used for the tests. A custom 0.019 x 0.025" stainless steel straight wire chuck was prepared. Four supports are edged to a rigid metal base plate at 8 mm intervals with 16 mm space for a movable support in the center. The evaluation was done according to the test protocol described by Tidy⁶ as shown in Figures 1 and 2.

Fig 1: Bracket-wire combination setup

Fig 2: universal testing Machine (Instron 5848)

The arc was secured with wire ligatures. The lock holes were positioned against the obstacle, followed by arches of stainless steel, nickel, titanium and TMA. A total of 180 readings from the lock wire were taken for the study. Each lock was tested only once and each wire sample was passed through only one lock to eliminate the effect of wear. Therefore, for each lock-arch combination, the test was run ten times and the mean was recorded. The ligature on the movable slide was initially fully tightened then loosened to allow it to slide freely. The movable cantilever was equipped with a 10 mm drive arm on which a weight could be suspended representing a single equivalent force in the center, representing the distance from the gap to the center of resistance of a typical canine tooth. All tests were conducted under dry conditions on an Instron test machine (model 5848) with the bar moving downward at 2 mm / min. The movable support was suspended from the load cell of the testing machine while the metal base plate moved down with the crossbar to which it was mounted. In each test, the support was moved a distance of not less than 2.5 mm across the center space and the load cell reading was recorded on

graph paper. The weight suspended from the drive arm provided a load of 100 g. The load readings represented the clinical retraction force that would be applied to the tooth, some of which would be lost to friction and the remainder transferred to the root of the tooth. At the start of each test, an unloaded test on the support arm was performed to verify that the wire ligature was bent on the arc. During each test, a load versus deflection plot was plotted on the computer with the x axis representing the movement of the buckle in millimeters and the y axis representing the load in newtons. The initial peak of the graph was taken as static friction and the kinetic friction was determined by averaging five readings on the Y axis at constant time intervals.

RESULT:

Descriptive statistics were calculated, including the mean and standard deviation of the static and kinetic friction forces for all types of lock-arch combinations. The values of the static and kinetic frictional forces are shown in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

Table 1: descriptive statistics of static and kinetic frictional forces for stainless steel bracket

Frictional force	archwire	n	Mean	sd	seM	Min	Max	F-value	p-value
static peak (gm)	SS	20	157.85	103.42	23.13	38.75	450.71	11.25	0.000*
	NiTi	20	246.00	117.51	26.28	47.93	455.81		
	TMA	20	321.76	106.69	23.86	153.97	462.94		
avg. Kinetic friction (gm)	SS	20	138.35	95.92	21.45	72.40	494.55	12.73	0.000*
	NiTi	20	239.26	101.61	22.72	108.33	489.46		
	TMA	20	280.63	75.63	16.91	92.28	404.82		

Table 2: descriptive statistics of static and kinetic frictional forces for ceramic bracket

Frictional force	archwire	n	Mean	sd	seM	Min	Max	F-value	p-value
static peak (gm)	SS	20	212.40	144.00	32.20	138.68	537.38	12.407	0.000*
	NiTi	20	295.25	83.36	18.64	41.81	427.25		
	TMA	20	365.56	27.15	6.07	305.91	383.41		
avg. Kinetic friction (gm)	SS	20	208.11	124.84	27.92	137.25	450.95	11.618	0.000*
	NiTi	20	284.35	24.70	5.52	203.94	302.04		
	TMA	20	321.98	34.46	7.70	298.16	392.58		

Table 3: descriptive statistics of static and kinetic frictional forces self-ligating bracket

Frictional force	archwire	n	Mean	sd	seM	Min	Max	F-value	p- value
static peak (gm)	SS	20	135.00	72.45	16.20	32.63	299.79	14.526	0.000*
	NiTi	20	193.79	76.91	17.20	32.63	333.44		
	TMA	20	259.92	70.47	15.77	139.70	337.52		
avg. Kinetic friction (gm)	SS	20	113.10	50.43	11.28	39.77	194.76	8.934	0.000*
	NiTi	20	162.84	52.97	11.85	74.44	250.64		
	TMA	20	194.37	76.99	17.21	96.46	305.91		

One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and post hoc test were performed to evaluate the difference between the means of different brackets with different arcuate wires as shown in Tables 4, 5 and 6.

Table 4: comparison of static and kinetic frictional forces of stainless steel archwire with different types of brackets

Frictional force	archwire	Bracket type	Mean difference	sig
static peak (gm)	SS	SS	54.55	0.271
		Self-ligating	77.39	0.077
	SS	Ceramic	- 54.55	0.271
		Self-ligating	22.84	0.791
	SS	Ceramic	- 77.39	0.077
		SS	- 22.84	0.791
avg. Kinetic friction (gm)	SS	SS	69.76	0.062
		Self-ligating	95.01	0.007*
	SS	Ceramic	- 69.76	0.062
		Self-ligating	25.25	0.682
	SS	Ceramic	- 95.01	0.007*
		SS	- 25.25	0.682

Table 5: comparison of static and kinetic frictional forces of niti archwire with different types of brackets

Frictional force	archwire	Bracket type	Mean difference	sig
static peak (gm)	NiTi	SS	49.25	0.233
		Self-ligating	101.46	0.003*
	NiTi	Ceramic	- 49.25	0.233
		Self-ligating	52.20	0.196
	NiTi	Ceramic	- 101.46	0.003*
		SS	- 52.20	0.196
avg. Kinetic friction (gm)	NiTi	SS	45.08	0.097
		Self-ligating	121.51	0.000*
	NiTi	Ceramic	- 45.08	0.097
		Self-ligating	76.43	0.002*
	NiTi	Ceramic	- 121.51	0.000*
		SS	- 76.43	0.002*

Table 6: comparison of static and kinetic frictional force of tMa archwire with different types of brackets

Frictional force	archwire	Bracket type	Mean difference	sig
static peak (gm)	TMA	SS	43.79	0.167
		Self-ligating	105.64	0.000*
	TMA	Ceramic	- 43.79	0.167
		Self-ligating	61.84(*)	0.032
	TMA	Ceramic	- 105.64	0.000*
		SS	- 61.84	0.032*
avg. Kinetic friction (gm)	TMA	SS	41.35	0.122
		Self-ligating	127.60	0.000*
	TMA	Ceramic	- 41.35	0.122
		Self-ligating	86.25	0.000*
	TMA	Ceramic	- 127.60	0.000*
		SS	- 86.25	0.000*

DISCUSSION:

In orthodontic mechanotherapy, the biological response of the tissue to the resulting tooth movement will only occur if the applied forces adequately overcome the friction at the interface of the bracket wire⁹⁻¹⁰. This means that the force required to move the tooth through the bracket against the wire causes friction located at the interface of the bracket wire, which may prevent optimal force from being achieved in the support tissue¹¹. Therefore, orthodontists must have a quantitative assessment of the orthodontic forces encountered in order to achieve a precise level of force and obtain the optimal biological response for effective tooth movement. In the presented research, the mean value of static and kinetic friction of a stainless steel (Gemini) lock with a stainless-steel wire of 0.019 × 0.025" showed a significant result for all types of arches (p <0.05) (Table 1, Graph 1). When the suction wire 0.019 × 0.025 "was compared to the NiTi and TMA wire of the same size (Table 1); the difference in forces needed to move the buckle along the wire increased significantly, with stainless steel requiring the least force and titanium beta requiring the most. These differences were judged to be due to the surface roughness. It turns out that stainless steel provides significantly less frictional resistance than NiTi and beta titanium. This report is consistent with the study by Garner et al who showed that beta - titanium and NiTi wires were more resistant to sliding in stainless steel brackets than stainless steel wires when tested without anguling the brackets¹². This report is in line with the research by Kusa et al who found that a stainless-steel lock with a stainless-steel arc wire, which renders the surface chemically passive due to the formation of a chromium oxide layer, favors

a lower coefficient of friction than stainless steel arch locks made of beta-titanium. It has been found that the frictional resistance (FR) of ceramic brackets is increased by their surface roughness. In the presented research, the mean value of static and kinetic friction of a ceramic lock (Clarity) with a stainless-steel arc 0.019 × 0.025" showed a statistically significant difference for all types of wires (p <0.05) (Table 2, Diagram 2). In this study, beta-titanium arcs generated greater friction than stainless steel and nickel-titanium arcs in ceramic lock-arch joints. This is consistent with the studies by Loftus et al. And Prosocki et al.; reported that the increased friction in the case of beta-titanium wire may be due to the wire sticking to the material of the breech slit. The Damon Self-ligating bracket is a second-generation self-ligating bracket that does not apply spring pressure to the bow. This bracket uses a self-ligating arch wire sheath that slides vertically in the occlusal direction in the upper arch and gingival in the lower arch¹³. In the presented research, the mean value of static and kinetic friction of self-ligating brackets (Damon) with a stainless-steel arch of 0.019 × 0.025" showed a statistically significant difference for all arches (p <0.05). Thus, the frictional forces increased in the order of SS, NiTi, and TMA, and there was a significant difference in the frictional force between NiTi and TMA wires. (Table 3, Graph 3). This is in line with a study by Kusy et al who observed similar trends for stainless steel locks with these alloys. The high friction associated with the TMA wire is attributed to the high titanium content and surface reactivity which causes adhesion during sliding mechanics. Kusy showed that the surface texture of NiTi wire is rougher than TMA and SS, but the friction characteristics do not follow a similar

pattern, according to a study by Porosoki¹⁴. Our research is supported by previous reports according to which NiTi wire showed a greater friction force than SS wire with self-ligating locks. The current in vitro study showed that self-ligating brackets had significantly lower static and kinetic frictional forces than ceramic and stainless-steel brackets in all arc alloy combinations. This is in line with the research by Loftus and Shivpuja. Stainless steel brackets had the lowest frictional force than ceramic brackets, which may be due to the properties of the metal which allow for better polishing and a smoother surface. The difference in frictional forces between a ceramic bracket with a metal-reinforced gap and a stainless-steel bracket may be due to the difficulty of matching the metal to the ceramic and their different coefficients of expansion. This is in line with studies by Loftus, Ho, Downing, Kusy. The lowest frictional force generated by the self-ligating bracket can be explained by the difference in the structure of the bracket body, as well as the material composition of the bracket and cap gap. This is in line with a study by Shivpuja. Another possible cause of the low friction of the self-ligating bracket may be that the lip guard may not be in contact with the arc wire, thus eliminating one source of normal force caused by common stainless-steel pressure. This is consistent with the research of Berger et al., Sims et al. The use of self-ligating brackets solves two important issues of orthodontists. Friction resistance drop; both static and dynamic are beneficial to hard and soft tissues and shorten treatment time. Self-ligating bracket systems are advantageous because they do not cause poor oral hygiene, as with elastomeric bands, and eliminate the possibility of injury to the patient and the orthodontist by using stainless steel bands¹⁵.

CONCLUSION:

The following conclusions were drawn from this study:

1. Self-ligating brackets (Damon) generated much lower static and kinetic friction forces than stainless steel (Gemini) and ceramic (Clarity) brackets.
2. Static friction was more than kinetic friction in all archwire-bracket combinations.
3. Among the archwire materials, beta-titanium showed the highest frictional force and the stainless steel arc showed the lowest.

REFERENCES:

1. Kolge, Neeraj E., Vivek J. Patni, Girish Karandikar, Prateek Daga, and Aarti B. Madhaswar. "Comparative Evaluation of Dimensional Accuracy, Surface Characteristics, and Load Deflection Attributes of 0.019"× 0.025"

Stainless Steel Wires Sourced from Six Different Commercial Houses: An In Vitro Study." *Journal of Indian Orthodontic Society* 54, no. 4 (2020): 311-320.

2. Sahany, Subrat Kumar, and G. Sreejith Kumar. "An In Vitro Evaluation of Frictional Characteristics of Labial and Lingual Self-ligating Brackets with Various Archwire Alloys." *Journal of Indian Orthodontic Society* 54, no. 3 (2020): 203-213.
3. El-Bialy, Tarek, Ahmad Alobeid, Cornelius Dirk, Andreas Jäger, Ludger Keilig, and Christoph Bourauel. "Comparison of force loss due to friction of different wire sizes and materials in conventional and new self-ligating orthodontic brackets during simulated canine retraction." *Journal of Orofacial Orthopedics/Fortschritte der Kieferorthopädie* 80, no. 2 (2019): 68-78.
4. Yousif, Atia A., and Usama M. Abdel Karim. "Assessment of friction resistance of four orthodontic arch wires using three ligation methods in dry and wet conditions." *Egyptian Orthodontic Journal* 50, no. December 2016 (2020): 85-102.
5. PILON, Juliano, Ana Rosa COSTA, Lourenço CORRER-SOBRINHO, Mário VEDOVELLO FILHO, and Heloísa Cristina VALDRIGHI. "A comparative analysis of the frictional resistance of esthetic orthodontic wires." *Revista de Odontologia da UNESP* 48 (2019).
6. Barbosa, William Carlos Silva, Américo Bortolazzo Correr, Diego Patrik Alves Carneiro, Mário Vedovello Filho, Ana Paula Terossi de Godoi, and Heloísa Cristina Valdrighi. "Evaluation of friction on self-ligating and conventional brackets associated with different types of archwires submitted to sliding mechanics." *Brazilian Journal of Oral Sciences* 18 (2019): e191605-e191605.
7. Desai, Hina, Fenil Manishkumar Gandhi, Kalpesh Patel, and Sarvesh Agrawal. "Comparison of friction in sliding mechanics using different ligation methods on ceramic bracket with metal slot and epoxy resin-coated stainless steel esthetic wire: An in vitro study." *Journal of Indian Orthodontic Society* 53, no. 2 (2019): 101-108.
8. Francisconi, Manoela-Fávaro, Guilherme Janson, Karina-Maria José-Fernando-Castanha Henriques, and Salvatore Freitas. "Evaluation of the force generated by gradual deflection of 0.016-inch NiTi and stainless steel orthodontic wires in self-ligating metallic and esthetic brackets." *Journal of clinical and experimental dentistry* 11, no. 5 (2019): e464.

9. Abi Dergham, Carine, Elie Khoury, and Joseph Ghoubri. "In vitro comparison of frictional forces of a new polycrystalline ceramic bracket versus metal-insert ceramic bracket before and after aging." *International orthodontics* 17, no. 2 (2019): 202-207.
10. Ranpura, Krishna, Sangeeta Shah, Dhaval Somani, Keyur Soni, Tilak Parikh, and Sejal Patel. "Assessment of minimum force required to initiate sliding of stainless steel wire in ceramic (monocrystalline and polycrystalline) and stainless steel preadjusted edgewise brackets using stainless steel and elastomeric ligation techniques—An in vitro study." *International Journal of Preventive and Clinical Dental Research* 7, no. 2 (2020): 17.
11. Alsabti, Nouf, and Nabeel Talic. "Comparison of Static Friction and Surface Topography of Low Friction and Conventional TMA Orthodontic Arch Wires: An In-Vitro Study." *The Saudi Dental Journal* (2020).
12. Haverkos, Stephen M. "Frictional Properties of Novel Bracket Systems: An In-vitro Study." (2019).
13. CAI, YONGQING. "EFFECTS OF THE INSERTION OF AN ARCHWIRE THIN-WALLED SLEEVE IN ACCELERATING THE CANINE'S TRANSLATION." *Journal of Mechanics in Medicine and Biology* (2020): 2040009.
14. Park, Choon-Soo, Hyung-Seog Yu, Jung-Yul Cha, Sung-Seo Mo, and Kee-Joon Lee. "Effect of archwire stiffness and friction on maxillary posterior segment displacement during anterior segment retraction: A three-dimensional finite element analysis." *The Korean Journal of Orthodontics* 49, no. 6 (2019): 393-403.
15. Sayar, Gülşilay, Yıldız Öztürk Ortan, and Bülent Aydemir. "İZMİR DEMOCRACY UNIVERSITY HEALTH SCIENCES JOURNAL IDUHES."